

It's alive: An empirical study on animism and animacy in product design

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Abstract The attachment people experience towards products has been the topic of many studies but very little has been written on *animism and product attachment*. Here it is argued that in order to grant a product animated qualities, the user actually requires animistic thinking and it is necessary to translate perceivable characteristics of *animacy* into product language. This is the basis for empirically testing the mutually dependent relationship (of *animism* and *animacy*) using six separate experiments. The hypotheses to be tested assume that a product featuring a defined characteristic is perceived as more alive or more animated than the same product lacking such a characteristic. It is argued here that more product attachment can be achieved not simply through more things “alive” but by actually encouraging a *new animism*.

Keywords *Animism, Animacy, Evolutionary theory, Product design, Product attachment*

Introduction

Our modern consumerism leads to shorter lifespans of products in most categories since older versions of the products are often replaced while still functioning and new products are bought following the slogan „the cheaper, the better“. This is not only the result of planned obsolescence (Packard 1960), but also of obsolescence of desirability. To avoid ecological disaster, some approaches have been suggested: The *Cradle to Cradle* concept (McDonough & Braungart 2010, 2013) as well as *Circular Product Design* (Bakker, 2014) are amongst the most promising. Foremost, this paper is influenced by Jonathan Chapman’s theory of emotionally durable design where the relationships between consumer and product are explored (Chapman 2005, 2009, 2015). Although such considerations are indispensable for a needed design revolution, this paper argues for more attachment to the things we already have. As the things around us become “alive”, is it not feasible to expect more emotionality? The easiest way to encourage the perception of life in products likely is through a product’s appearance and behavior since some crucial criteria for life – such as DNA – cannot be observed. In biological language, we work on the phenotype and not the genotype of an object. In order to focus more on *animacy*, we defined seven characteristics based on Koshland (2002), Bell (2012a, 2012b) and Moskowitz (2012): adaptability, energy, goal-oriented movement, memory, regeneration, sensation and communication. To test which characteristics are required of a product for it to be considered alive we designed a laboratory study and analyzed the findings with regard to design strategies.

Animism and our archaic mind

Any sufficiently advanced technology is indistinguishable from magic. – Arthur C. Clarke (1962)

Talking to inanimate objects is nothing new and humans have likely always done so, but that communication has just transmuted to a dialogue. As our tools’ communication improves, users move in a little closer to listen and respond. We already pinch, tap, touch, hold and talk to our devices and it seems that ironically, Modernity has returned to *animism*, the belief in a soul inside inanimate objects.

The British anthropologist Edward Tylor first articulated the term *animism* calling it the “idea of pervading life and will in nature” (Tylor, 1871). According to Tylor, animism was the most primitive stage in belief systems, followed by a polytheistic and final monotheistic stage. Not an organized religion, to Tylor animism has no institution (e.g. a synagogue, mosque, or church), it does not have an unchangeable doctrine (e.g. a belief in a son of God), and it doesn’t have sacred literature (e.g. the Hebrew Bible or the Quran). From the Latin *anima* (“breath, spirit, life”) it became known as the belief in the possession of a spiritual essence or soul of non-human entities such as animals, plants or inanimate objects. Remarkably, a vast majority of cultures do not have a term for such belief and even the described practitioners of animism do not use the term, suggesting that the phenomenon is little more than a European construct of the 19th century. Undeniably, the term *animism* now stands for traditionalism and for an outdated, even absurd practice. The term also became part of a larger construct of the notion of a time before and after bestowing souls onto things, a time before and after Modernity and nothing more than an anthropological curiosity. Ever since the Enlightenment, modern Europeans have decided to think in terms of subject-object dualism but such a mode of classification was just that: a classification. To a large degree Modernism is actually based on objectifying nature, of doing away with any notion of a subject-subject based relationship. And thus, *animism* – as defined in the

19th century – actually rejects Cartesian dualism and is anchored in the esoteric, non-scientific traditions. Philosopher Bruno Latour laments that we are living in times of wrong epistemologies:

“If there is one thing to wonder about in the history of Modernism, it is not that there are still people “mad enough to believe in animism”, but that so many hard headed thinkers have invented what should be called inanimism and have tied to this sheer impossibility their definition of what it is to be “rational” and “scientific”. It is inanimism that is the queer invention: an agency without agency constantly denied by practice” (Latour, 2010, p. 10).

The danger and far-reaching consequences of such constructed dualities becomes apparent when considering that *unilineal evolutionism* is intrinsically related to *modernization theory* (Rostow, 1990) via the writings of the so-called *neo-evolutionists* (White, 1954). In its final consequence, the idea that all civilizations imperatively have to move through the same stages of development is causally linked to world developmental politics as well as the industrial exploitation of nature. Indeed, the technophile tendencies so rampant in design practices have been diametrically opposed to E.O. Wilson’s “biophilia” (Stairs, 1997).

Recently, anthropologists and comparative-religion scholars have re-defined *animism* to mean something different (Bird-David 1999; Descola 2005, 2006, 2009; Harvey 2005; Ingold 2000). Our relationships with the world and the frontiers between human and nonhuman – even between living and non-living – are being reconsidered. Similarly, the dichotomy of a *before* and *after* in history is senseless. A modern, rational mind never replaced a superstitious, primitive one just like the conquistadores of various eras and nations never found savages on lower evolutionist strata. In short, mistaken epistemologies aren’t replaced. Rather, the human mind perceives and makes sense of the world on different levels of abstraction simultaneously and it is thus important to inject the above epistemological discussions with some biological considerations.

Here we won’t satisfactorily answer the question whether humans are naturally prone to animism, but we can assume that the human species – like all living organism – is a complex product of evolution. We are so good at reasoning on the basis of design from birth onward that it is very likely a genetically evolved adaptation (Wilson, 2011), and thus each one of us truly is a designer. At the dawn of speciation, *Homo habilis* developed the first artifacts, culture was synonymous with design and the designer was Promethean. Ancestral Hominids have failed to evolve many defensive characteristics (Lorenz, 2000), but without a doubt they advanced to become the species most sophisticated at niche construction since we deliberately change most aspects of our environment (Odling-Smee, Laland, & Feldman, 2003). The blueprint for the things we design – hand axes, houses and smartphones – is never genetically anchored but the potential to shape existing matter into new forms and

in new ways likely is. Dennis Dutton believes all forms of design including art are innate, speaks of an *art-instinct* and argues that the production and acquisition of aesthetic objects has brought our ancestors a survival advantage (Dutton, 2009). As will be discussed in more detail below, the designer has to design for the circumstances of the 21st century but he/she should never forget that the end user has an archaic mind.

Product attachment and animacy

A lot of research has been done on designing meaningful and emotionally durable products in order to counteract the modern „throw-away culture“, mainly since the early 1980s and sometimes under different designations (e.g. Schultz, Kleine, & Kernan, 1989; Chapman, 2005, 2009, 2015; Mugge, 2007; Schifferstein & Zwartzkruis-Pelgrim, 2008, Page, 2014). Also, affective sustainability of objects – in other words, the object itself causing sustainable behavior in its user – has been researched (Börjesson, 2009). By considering cognition part of the design process, our everyday things might be longer lasting by adding *animacy* (Norman, 2004). Perhaps the most important researcher in this field, Jonathan Chapman defines waste as a failed relationship between user and object (Chapman, 2015, p. 20). While the first period (“honeymoon”) of possession (e.g. some weeks) between an owner and product is full of excitement, curiosity and interest, these emotions often fade in the course of time. This is often a result of disappointed demands on the products that were raised by advertising messages and decreasing novelty of the products themselves. Therefore the challenge is to keep the product developing and evolving side by side with its owner to preserve an attachment and to reach a longer-lasting honeymoon period full of passion and desire. According to Chapman five points should be considered to prolong an emotional relationship (Chapman, 2009):

- **Narrative:** *users share an evolving history with the product which is often related to the date or place of the acquisition (e.g. souvenirs) or from whom the user got it (e.g. as a present)*
- **Consciousness:** *the product possesses free will or an autonomous mind*
- **Attachment:** *users feel a strong emotional connection to the product which is connected to the service, information or meaning it provides*
- **Fiction:** *the product holds attention because the user cannot fully understand it or know it, especially with a recently bought item*
- **Surface:** *the product ages well and develops character through use (or sometimes misuse), e.g. patina.*

In this paper we focus on the concept *consciousness*, as it is believed that this factor is especially effective in warranting product attachment. We realized that the term *consciousness* is probably too ambitious since something has to be literally alive to be conscious. So we took a step back and stated that *consciousness* actually comes after life is put into something, animating it. The degree of being alive may vary depending on language and their cultural influences. In some languages a tree – for example –

may be seen as alive and in others as inanimate (Malchukov, 2008). Following such considerations, we chose the term *animacy* as “the state of being alive and animated” (Animacy, 2016). “To animate” is a transitive verb, and thus you always need a subject, which actively animates a passive object. Although not a commonly used word, *animacy* should delicately express that the artefact is not actually alive itself but was rather provided with “life” by somebody. “Giving life” is not meant in a procreative, but rather cognitive way. Animate cues are likely those that suggest intrinsic traits such as consciousness, intention, goal-orientation or others normally reserved for living organisms. The famous test by Heider and Simmel (1944) showed that simple geometric shapes (moving triangle, three moving circles and three non-moving squares) are considered animate due to their seeming intentionality. It was even demonstrated that a single, non-anthropomorphized, moving object can create the subjective impression of *animacy* (Tremoulet & Feldman, 2000).

Here, it is assumed that an object considered more alive will be less likely discarded. In order to produce an emotionally charged interface between subject and object, the designer must cater to the *animist* tendencies of the user, who then grants objects *animacy*. As is argued below, these processes are likely unconscious.

Evolution, animacy and the unconscious

It is an oxymoron to *study* the unconscious. For this reason its “discovery” by the founding fathers of psychoanalysis Freud and Jung was not part of the psychological canon until the 1970s when Richard Nisbett and Timothy Wilson demonstrated the difficulty humans have with introspection and/or explication of their own mental processes in a highly cited paper (Nisbett & Wilson, 1977). This phenomenon has actually been labeled “introspection illusion” and is considered a cognitive bias, often leading to a related illusion of superiority. In *Strangers to Ourselves*, Wilson (2004) develops a kind of method of self-knowledge based on action, not feelings or thoughts. Indeed, there are numerous other researchers who argue that intuition is a decision – making process for which reasoning is not consciously available (Bastick 1982, Agor 1986) but all neglect to explain *why* our unconscious might work the way it does. Why might it be adaptive?

Granting objects *animacy* likely happens on an unconscious level. In such a model, the observer must rely on a set of algorithms that grants *animacy* onto some entities but not others. Those algorithms – we believe – were put into place in our species’ evolutionary history due to advantageous outcomes for ancestral individuals. This reasoning belongs to *evolutionary psychology*, which, with its approach to the human psyche using principles of evolutionary theory, is controversial. However, without theoretical underpinning, granting *animacy* would simply be on a long list of illusions, heuristics and cognitive biases. The systematic evolutionary study of the human psyche is young (Barkow, Cosmides, & Tooby, 1992) and argues that Hominids living in small tribes of hunter-

gatherers evolved a psychology for archaic – not modern – circumstances. Science writer Michael Shermer puts it this way:

“What may seem like irrational behavior today may have actually been rational 100,000 years ago. Without an evolutionary perspective, the assumptions of *Homo economicus* – that “Economic Man” is rational, self-maximizing and efficient in making choices – make no sense” (Shermer, 2008).

The aim of evolutionary psychology is to understand the ultimate – not proximate – reasons humans do what they do and it has the following main tenets: (1) Our ancestors faced many dire challenges during our species’ evolutionary history and natural selection designed our ancestors’ neural circuits to solve them. (1) Only those ancestors that were able to solve problems passed their genes on and those genes were used to build more successful neural circuits. (3) Thus, our modern skulls literally house Stone Age minds. (4) Most of the activity in our minds is unconscious and hidden from us. (5) The mind is modular. Different types of neural circuits are all specialized for solving different adaptive problems (Dunbar & Barrett 2007). The question that remains is *why*...was recognizing *animacy* advantageous to our ancestors?

Seeing animals or faces in clouds or the man in the moon, and hearing messages on Black Sabbath records when played in reverse are examples of *paraidolia*, the perception of patterns within random data. *Faces in the Clouds: A new Theory of Religion*, a recent book sees *paraidolia* as part of *animism*, positing that this might be a fitting evolutionary explanation for the birth of religions (Guthrie, 2015). It seems that we might actually be wired to see life rather than no-life in things by default. In the (critical) words of Tim Ingold:

“Thus we have all evolved to be closet animists without of course realizing it. Intuitive non-animists have been selected out, due to unfortunate encounters with things that turned out to be more alive than anticipated” (Ingold, 2006: 11).

Study on characteristics for animacy in product design

Our hypotheses stated that an artefact featuring characteristics of *animacy* has a higher rating in vocabulary connected to being alive. This was tested for all characteristics individually. Even if seven characteristics were defined to be important for the perception of life in products, only six were tested since *communication* as a very broad and also well-established function in interactive products would have gone beyond the scope of this study.

All tests included pairs of objects, videos or illustrations, which differed in the degree of *animacy*: One (object or video) featured the characteristic to be tested, the other purposefully neglected it. Study participants filled out thirteen different questionnaires. One of these collected personal data like age and gender. The other twelve contained semantic differentials (Osgood, Suci, & Tannenbaum,

Figure 1. The room's setup with pictures of the different areas.

1957), with which the subject rated the objects, videos or images. Semantic differentials were used because of their flexibility, ease of use and because they require little time to be filled out by test persons. The differentials consisted of nine different value pairs, five of which were only distractors that were not analyzed (e.g. extraordinary – ordinary, organic – artificial, active – passive, innovative – traditional, attractive – repulsive). The other four pairs of words related to being alive (animate – inanimate and lively – lifeless) and to character and personality (personal – impersonal and characterful – characterless). Originally, the test was conducted in German but the words were translated for this research paper.

The testing took place on two consecutive days at the Salzburg University of Applied Sciences. Two people worked on this experiment: The test supervisor stayed in the room with the subject, introduced him to the test, used a remote control, handed out and collected the questionnaires (see Figure 1) while the assistant recruited the subjects.

The six tests

Adaptability

This experiment was designed to evaluate a product's ability to adapt to its environment and/or its user by itself. Here, the subject was confronted with nearly

identical looking pieces of foam. He/she was instructed to take the material into the hands to get to know it (see Figure 2). The first one (A) is a special foam that adapts to the pressure with which it is handled and takes the shape of the object which is pressed into it and it keeps it a few moments after the pressure is removed. The second cuboid (B) is made out of normal foam which returns to its original shape immediately.

Energy

To test the impact of a product's acquisition of energy on the perception of that object, two torches were chosen (see Figure 3). The torch on the left has a battery and a simple switch on its side whereas the torch on the right requires the test subject to turn the crank in order to power it. The subject was asked to turn on and rate the torches consecutively.

Figure 2. Setup for testing adaptability.

Figure 3. Three views of torches used to test energy.

Goal-oriented movement

Goal-oriented movement is movement of a product (or a part of the product) unambiguously dedicated to reach a goal. Two videos – inspired by the famous video from Heider and Simmel (1944) – were used. Both videos (see Figure 4 for a screenshot) feature one moving triangle, three moving circles and three non-moving squares. In one scene, the geometrical shapes seem to follow a goal while in another scene they do not. The black-and-white scenes take about 30 seconds.

Memory

An animated product should have the ability to learn and memorize things such as its owner’s habits and preferences. For this experiment the product’s behavior was presented with the help of a photo story, for the simple reason that testing this premise in real time would have been far too time-intensive for this experiment (see Figure 5). Both stories start with the same situation: The alarm clock rings, someone gets up. Then he turns on the coffee machine. He waits until the machine is ready to work. Then the user makes his coffee by starting the process, waiting and then stopping it when the desired amount of coffee is in the cup. Then the next cup is placed under the machine (a smaller one for the partner) and the user starts the process, waits then stops the machine when the desired amount of coffee is in the cup. This is

Figure 4. Screenshot from the video featuring goal-oriented movement.

followed by the statement “one week later”. At this point the stories start to diverge. In the first story the exact same situation as the one described before is shown again.

The second photo story (see Figure 6) starts with an alarm clock but then the situation changes. On the second photo the coffee machine switches itself on. Then the person gets up and pushes the first cup under the coffee machine. The machine recognizes the cup and starts to brew coffee autonomously, regulating the amount of coffee depending on cup size. The user can prepare breakfast while the coffee machine makes his coffee. When the machine is finished the user brings another cup for his partner. The machine again recognizes the cup and makes the coffee all by itself. When finished the machine will turn itself off.

Regeneration

This characteristic addresses the product’s ability to heal or repair itself from small damages – ideally without any help from the user. Regeneration can be

Figure 5. The first part of the photo story used to test memory.

Figure 6. The memory part from the photo story.

introduced to products through their materials. Due to the fact that most self-healing materials are still in development, two videos (see Figure 7) were used to show the effect the self-healing material has. One video shows a material, which gets scratched and stays scratched. The other one shows the very same material, which again gets scratched but this time is able to heal itself.

Sensation

For testing the impact sensation has on the perception of life a simple trick is used. Two similar lamps are placed on one table (see Figure 8). Both of them are plugged in and the subject is told to turn them on. One of them works in a traditional way with a switch to be turned on. The other one “senses” that the subject is near and it turns on by itself. This is accomplished using a remote control operated by the researcher without the subject’s knowledge.

Data analysis and findings

A total of 31 people were tested but a check on the consistency of the answers led to the exclusion of one

subject. The subjects’ (15f, 15m) age ranged from 18 to 42 (mean 24.00 ±5.99 years). The value pairs are rated from -3 to +3 with -3 meaning totally animate/lively/ personal/characterful and +3 meaning completely inanimate/lifeless/impersonal/characterless.

The following section shows the individual analyses for each tested characteristic and for each of the four relevant items.

Adaptability

In the experiment, this was the first tested characteristic. Table 1 shows that all four items show significant differences between the object with and the object without the characteristic adaptability. The standard deviations are quite high for every item.

Energy

The results for energy are similar to those for adaptability (see Table 2), but with a general lower standard deviation for each item. The differences between the two objects are again on a significant level.

Figure 7. Screenshots from the video which features regeneration.

Figure 8. Setup for testing sensation with the lamps used.

Goal-oriented movement

For goal-oriented movement, no significant differences could be found between the two videos for three of the four items (see Table 3). Only the item animate – inanimate was rated significantly different. The standard deviations are again high, especially for the item characterful – characterless.

Memory

The characteristic memory was rated significantly different between the two videos in three of the four items (see Table 4). Only the item characterful/characterless showed no significant difference and has also the highest standard deviation.

Table 1. *t*-test for adaptability (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	2.143	-6.134	.000
lively – lifeless	2.300	-6.032	.000
characterful – characterless	2.463	-4.597	.000
personal – impersonal	2.013	-3.991	.000

Table 2. *t*-test for energy (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	1.964	-7.623	.000
lively – lifeless	1.724	-6.885	.000
characterful – characterless	1.512	-6.158	.000
personal – impersonal	2.025	-4.417	.000

Table 3. *t*-test for goal-oriented movement (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	1.771	2.989	.006
lively – lifeless	2.096	1.481	.149
characterful – characterless	2.143	-1.022	.315
personal – impersonal	2.825	0.905	.373

Table 4. *t*-test for memory/learning (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	2.493	-4.761	.000
lively – lifeless	2.449	-5.070	.000
characterful – characterless	4.025	-1.270	.214
personal – impersonal	2.662	-3.018	.005

Figure 9. Rating for the four items for the objects featuring the characteristics.

Regeneration

Two of the four items (animate/inanimate and lively/lifeless) were rated significantly different between the two videos (see Table 5). The standard deviation for all items is quite moderate.

Sensation

All items for sensation prove a significant difference between the animated and the unanimated objects (see Table 6) with moderate standard deviations.

Looking at the overall findings, we created graphic profiles for the semantic differentials by evaluating the mean for each value pair and connecting the means with lines. Figure 9 shows this data for the animated objects/videos.

Figure 10 shows the ratings for the unanimated objects or videos. It is visible that the items were generally ranked with higher values. An exemption is the characteristic goal-oriented movement, which has remarkably low values for the items animate – inanimate, lively – lifeless and characterful – characterless.

To test our hypotheses we also did a two-tailed t-test for each characteristic and compared the ratings of the (averaged) four items between the animated and the unanimated object or video (see Table 7). The characteristic goal-oriented movement is the only one that shows no significant difference between the two videos. As a reminder, this characteristic was represented by a different behavior of geometrical objects.

The overall outcome of our statistical analyses confirms our hypotheses for five of six characteristics: adaptability, energy, memory, regeneration and sensation. The correspondent hypothesis for goal-oriented movement had to be rejected.

Interpretation and further observations

When asked, after finishing the tests, where they had experienced difficulties, three of the subjects mentioned rating qualities connecting to *animacy* (animate and lively) but the others had no problem related to these. Seven subjects thought rating organically – artificial (one of the distractor items) was especially difficult because all of the objects/videos were artificial. Seven subjects mentioned active – passive as

Table 5. t-test for regeneration (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	2.638	-4.014	.000
lively – lifeless	2.173	-5.965	.000
characterful – characterless	1.929	-0.189	.851
personal – impersonal	2.542	-1.736	.093

Table 6. t-test for sensation (animated object/video vs. unanimated object/video).

Item	Standard Deviation	T	p (two-tailed)
animate – inanimate	1.960	-9.037	.000
lively – lifeless	1.889	-10.052	.000
characterful – characterless	2.636	-2.355	.025
personal – impersonal	1.964	-5.392	.000

Figure 10. Rating for the four items for the objects not featuring the characteristics.

especially difficult to rate because, even if the instruction told them to rate the objects, some were not sure if they had to rate if the user (not the object) was active/passive or the object. Further, one person mentioned attractive – repulsive, personal – impersonal and innovative – traditional as difficult to rate.

Only the characteristic – goal-oriented movement – did not lead to a higher ranking of the vocabulary connected to being alive. An explanation for this might be that there is a little bit more movement in the not goal-oriented video than in the other one and each pentagon moves in a unique way. This, and especially the good rating of the video not featuring goal-oriented movement, could indicate that movement has an influence on the perception of life but it does not have to be goal-oriented. Additionally, it may not have been the right decision to ask the subjects to rate the whole sequence. The outcomes could be different if the instruction was to rate just the triangle. One participant mentioned that he perceived some kind of goal in both videos. He stated that the triangular in the first video is nice because it cares for the pentagons in some way. On the other hand he perceived the triangular in the second video as unfriendly. He stated that it came in and laid into the pentagons.

One subject stated that he perceived the coffee machine featuring memory/learning, the video featuring regeneration and the lamp featuring

Table 7. t-test for the characteristics.

Characteristic	t	p (two-tailed)
adaptability	-6.190	.000
energy	-8.955	.000
goal-oriented movement	1.346	.189
memory	-3.899	.001
regeneration	-4.463	.000
sensation	-8.403	.000

sensation as less personal than the regular ones. When looking at the mean ratings this statement was not proved right for the majority of the subjects.

For designers, these findings show that the characteristic here labeled as *animacy* can actually be injected into products. We see the use of regenerative materials and the addition of adaptive and interactive features as strong candidates for a new design process.

Conclusion: Designing for animism

The idea of designed animism actually dates back to the 1970s when design theorist treated the impact of pervasive computing on the human experience and design as a discipline (Laurel, 2003). Of late, approaches in design research have been steered towards purposely increasing emotional durability of products through design. As shown in a recent conference paper, *animism* can actually be used as an appropriate design metaphor for interactive design (Van Allen, McVeigh-Schultz, Brown, Kim, & Lara, 2013). Not all types of design share such intrinsic relationships with *animism*, but all would arguably benefit from the ongoing discussion of a new animism.

Additional research on the evolutionary accuracy of *animacy* is needed to address whether or not *animacy* is innate. Evolutionary psychology, as an explanatory framework could prove fruitful for approaching an answer.

Is *animism* something to be encouraged or renounced for society to work? The evolutionary process is not teleological and, as Popper remarked, “the future is open”. “Thus it is our duty, not to prophesy evil, but, rather, to fight for a better world,” he added (Popper, 1967). It is argued here that there can only be a better world with better design solutions. It is safe to say that humans have a deeply ingrained fascination with stuff, which has become a serious concern when considering the resources required making all such stuff. Animism, understood as a deeply rooted understanding of a world unfolding, alive with things could very well lead to a more sustainable future. Is it

possible that we have come so removed from the creation of the objects around us that we have dropped all parenthood-like affection? Industrialization and in a sense industrial design have removed the production of things by one degree creating a system where things are mothered by things. Further research might address any correlation between the Cartesian dualism and the Industrial era.

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